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Studies on Scurvy

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III. SOME CHARACTERISTICS OF THE BLOOD OF THE GUINEA PIG IN EXPERIMENTAL SCURVY¹

By LEWIS M. McCORMICK

This study of the blood of scorbutic guinea pigs was undertaken at the suggestion and with the co-operation of Dr. Meyer, to determine the presence of hematological changes in a deficiency condition "which, if not true scurvy, is indistinguishable from it at present," according to Holst and Frölich '12.

Hess '20 stated that a characteristic secondary anemia accompanies scurvy in man and wrote as follows: "Hemoglobin is diminished far out of proportion to the decrease in the number of red cells. There may be polycythemia. Microscopically, the red blood cells show poikilocytosis, anisocytosis, and a lack of hemoglobin; they are slightly enlarged, with the occasional occurrence of exceptionally large cells resembling the dropsical cells described in connection with chlorosis. Sometimes a few nucleated red cells and myeloblasts are seen. . . . The dropsical cells suggest a disturbance of the salt balance in the plasma.

"In some cases we have found a decreased fragility of the red cells, which also has been described in chlorosis. The total number of leucocytes is slightly increased. In our cases the mononuclear cells have averaged 66%. . . . Labor described an oesinophilia during convalescence, a phenomenon which we have not encountered. Some describe a marked increase in the polynuclear cells, which probably is to be regarded as a reaction to secondary infection. There is indeed a marked difference of opinion in regard to the morphology of the blood in scurvy in adults as well as in infants. . . . The divergent reports probably should be attributed to the fact that the investigators are describing scurvy in various grades of severity, of different stages of development, or complicated by intercurrent disease."

Liotta '23 found in the guinea pig that the large mononuclear cells increase progressively, that the eosinophiles also increase in a still less degree. However, in some cases in man, Eichhorst '13-'14, and Liotta in the guinea pig also, found a regular diminution of the erythrocytes. Leitner '17 and Montanari 1821 regularly obtained leucopenia with some lymphocytosis, in man.

These conflicting findings seem to suggest that the changes in the blood characteristic of scurvy should perhaps be sought in the cell picture rather than in the cell count.

¹ This investigation was supported in part by a grant to Dr. Meyer from the Committee on Research of the American Medical Association.

PROCEDURE

My first series consisted of twenty healthy guinea pigs of mixed strain, of varying age, and of both sexes. These were put on an abundant diet of raw alfalfa, raw barley, and water. Although some vitamine C exists in such feed, we know that animals do not get a sufficient quantity of it while on this diet to prevent relatively early death.

A second series of sixteen pigs was divided into four groups of four pigs each, and fed as follows:

Series 2, Group I—raw alfalfa, water, and orange juice.

Group II—raw alfalfa, raw barley, water, and wheat germ.

Group III—raw alfalfa, raw barley, and water.

Group IV—raw alfalfa, raw barley, water, and greens.

Orange juice supplied vitamins A, B, and C to the diet (Sherman and Smith '22) of the first group. Substitution of wheat germ for the orange juice supplied only vitamins A and B (Eddy '21) to the second group. Groups III and IV were run as controls, the diet of the former being deficient in vitamins B and C and possibly A, as in Series 1, and that of the latter being a normal diet containing all of the vitamins.

Tests as given below were continued till within several hours before the expected death of an animal, when it was gassed and necropsied, except those in Groups I and IV of Series 2.

The procedure used in making these tests was as follows:

Both ears of the guinea pig were shaved and washed thoroughly with soap and water before the beginning of the experiment. The washing was repeated as gently and carefully as possible about fifteen minutes before each sample of blood was taken, and this washing was followed by further gentle cleansing with 95 per cent alcohol. A cut was made with a sterile spring lancet and a natural flow of blood obtained. No sample of blood was taken while the animal was excited or struggling, and all were taken successively and as rapidly as possible for making fragility tests, the estimations of hemoglobin, erythrocyte and leucocyte counts, and smears for differential white cell counts, and for nucleated and reticulated erythrocyte counts. The rectal temperature was taken as the last step.

RED BLOOD CELL COUNT

A certified Leitz hemocytometer was used. The pipette and counting chamber were thoroughly cleansed by a solution of sulphuric acid and potassium dichromate, water, and alcohol. A sample of blood taken after the first two drops had been removed was drawn to the index "0.5" on the Thoma Blood Diluting Pipette with great care. While doing this, the pipette was held horizontally and at right angles to the line of vision so

that the exact height of the column could be easily seen and the tip submerged to avoid entrance of air-bubbles. If the blood went slightly beyond the mark, the tip of the pipette was touched to a moistened, clean cloth or the tip of the finger until the "0.5" mark was reached. The pipette was then quickly wiped off, and plunged into Hayem's Diluting Solution and this drawn up to the mark 101, with a slight rotation of the pipette, thus diluting the blood 1:200. The pipette was shaken vigorously transversely for temporary mixing, after which a heavy rubber band was placed around the ends and the apparatus was laid down in a horizontal position.

After removing the rubber band several minutes later the pipette was shaken transversely for five minutes and three or four drops were expelled and a small drop placed upon the Double Neubauer counting chamber. The counting chamber and cover slip were cleaned and dried so that when they were placed in position Newton's color rings were visible. Immediately after the drops were in place the cover slip was quickly applied in an oblique manner and the Newton color rings again observed. The counting chamber was placed on the stage of the microscope, in a level position, and after about three minutes, to allow for settling of corpuscles, the counting was done provided the corpuscles were evenly distributed over the entire field and no air bubbles were present. Otherwise, the pipette was again shaken for five minutes and the process repeated. The counting was made with low-power magnification.

The cell count was made in five sets of sixteen squares each, taken from the corners and middle of the counting chamber. The cells on both counting planes were enumerated. If the count in the five sets of squares varied more than twenty or the total count in the eighty squares did not vary less than ten, a new sample of the mixture was taken and the whole process repeated.

To calculate the number of red-blood cells per cubic millimeter the total number in the eighty squares was divided by eighty to get the average per square. By multiplying this average by 400 (the area of each square being 1/400 sq. mm.) and by 10 (the depth of each square being 1/10 mm.) and by 200 (the extent of the dilution) the number of cells per cubic millimeter was obtained, as indicated in the following example:

$$\frac{543 \times 400 \times 10 \times 200}{80} = 5,430,000$$

According to Gulland and Goodall '25, "When the dilution is 1 in 200, the addition of four cyphers to the number of corpuscles counted in eighty squares at once gives the number per cmm."

The average difference in a series of preliminary counts made on myself was 2 per cent.

ESTIMATION OF HEMOGLOBIN

The hemoglobin determination was made with a Sahli-Leitz Nonfade Hemometer. This instrument consists of two solid glass comparison cylinders vertically arranged and a graduated test tube of the same diameter, and a pipette of 20 cmm. capacity. The graduated test tube is placed between the standard solid cylinders and the three held in a black frame with a white ground-glass background.

A tenth normal solution of hydrochloric acid was placed in the graduated tube to the mark "10." A drop of blood was obtained from the ear of the pig immediately after the specimen for the erythrocyte count was taken and drawn into the pipette to the 20 cmm. mark. The tip of the pipette was wiped off and the contents were blown into the graduated tube. This was followed by three washings of the pipette with distilled water. These washings were mixed with the chamber contents and the whole permitted to stand for two minutes. After this interval distilled water was added drop by drop with thorough mixing, until the color matched the color of the solid comparison cylinders.

In this method the hemoglobin is changed to acid hematin, the color of which is light brown and very easily matched. The percentage of hemoglobin is read directly.

The average difference in a series of preliminary estimations made on myself was 3 per cent.

COLOR INDEX

The color index was determined after the usual manner, by dividing the first three figures of the blood count by five and then dividing the percentage hemoglobin by the resulting number. This method is expressed in the following formula:

$$C.I. = \frac{\% Hb}{\% RBC} = \frac{\% Hb}{RBC \text{ count} \div 5,000,000}$$

This indicates the percentage of hemoglobin contained in each red corpuscle as compared to the normal.

WHITE BLOOD CELL COUNT

The leucocyte count was made with the same hemocytometer used for the erythrocyte count.

A sample of blood was taken from the same incision made for the red blood cell count and hemoglobin and the same steps were followed and cautions observed as in the case of drawing the erythrocyte samples. The blood was drawn to the "1" mark on the white-blood pipette and diluted with a 1 per cent solution of glacial acetic acid in distilled water to which

enough of methyl green had been added to color the solution a fairly deep green. The acid rendered the nuclear outlines sharp and the methyl green tinted them faintly.

The procedure followed was that used in counting the red cells.

Cells included in the total twenty-five sets of sixteen squares were counted. The total number of squares was 400.

A mechanical stage was used for counting both the red and white blood cells.

By dividing the total number of cells in the 400 squares by 400, the average number of cells per square was obtained. Multiplying this average by 400 (the area of each square being $1/400$ mm.) and by 10 (the depth of each square being $1/10$ mm.) and by 10 (the extent of the dilution) the number of cells per cubic millimeter was obtained.

Example :

$$\frac{70 \times 400 \times 10 \times 10}{400} = 7,000 \text{ per cmm.}$$

When the dilution is 1 to 10 the total number of cells in the squares multiplied by 100 gives the number per cubic millimeter.

A series of preliminary counts on myself showed an average difference in the counts to be about 5 per cent.

PREPARATION OF SMEARS

The slides used for making the smears were thoroughly washed with soap and water, rinsed well, and placed in sulphuric acid and dichromate solution for a couple of days. They were then thoroughly washed with hot water, dried on a clean cloth, and placed in 95 per cent alcohol for about twenty-four hours, wiped and dried over a Bunsen burner and stored carefully for future use.

A very small drop of blood was placed on one end of the slide, and half of a white cigarette paper which had been cut transversely was laid down longitudinally and obliquely just behind the drop of blood. As soon as the drop was touched it spread along the under surface of the paper when the latter was gently pulled across the slide. The paper was raised more vertically as it traveled along. In this manner a very even smear was obtained.

The smears were fixed in the open air at room temperature for about an hour and placed in acetone-free methyl alcohol. They usually remained in this solution up to one hour after which they were removed and again dried in the open air for a couple of minutes. They were stained with Jenner-Giemsa stain, a combination of Jenner's and Giemsa's methods. The Jenner solution brought out the neutrophilic and eosinophilic granules,

while the Giemsa stain intensified the mast-cell granules and defined the nuclear structure.

The smears were stained in Jenner's stain for three minutes, then in equal parts of Jenner's stain and distilled water for one minute, washed, and transferred to a dilute Giemsa solution (15 drops of Giemsa solution to 10 cc. of distilled water) and left for fifteen minutes, after which they were washed in distilled water and dried.

This method, as described by Gulland and Goodall, is excellent for the staining of the white as well as for nucleated red cells. Three hundred white blood cells were counted for the differential white count. A "tally-register" was used to assure greater accuracy in counting the nucleated and reticulated red blood cells as well.

For the study of red blood cell destruction, smears were made and fixed as above and stained with eosin and methylene blue.

RETICULATED ERYTHROCYTES

The reticulum of the red blood cell was stained by the Widal-Abrami and Brule method. The solution was made with 10 cc. of Unna's polychrome stain; 10 cc. of 0.8 per cent NaCl, and 10 cc. of 2 per cent sodium oxalate. Three cubic centimeters of this mixture were placed in a graduated centrifuge tube with three or four drops of blood. This was thoroughly mixed and allowed to stand for about ten minutes, after which it was centrifuged. The supernatant fluid was poured off carefully and smears were made from the sediment and dried over an alcohol flame. This made a very fine stain, but it faded in about four to six weeks. The cytoplasm of the cell stains a very pale blue, while the reticulum stains midnight blue. One thousand cells were counted for these determinations.

FRAGILITY AND HEMOLYSIS OF ERYTHROCYTES

A salt solution (2,000 cc.) of 0.5 per cent was prepared for all determinations enumerated below.

A series of twelve small test tubes in a rack was arranged and numbered from 14 to 25 inclusive. Two burettes with a very small capillary bore at the stopcock were used—one containing 0.5 per cent NaCl and the other distilled water. These two burettes were marked and after each day's work both were cleansed and allowed to drain and dry for the following day.

The NaCl solution in the burette was now placed in the numbered test tubes, as many drops as indicated by its number being placed in each tube, e.g., Number 14 would receive 14 drops while 25 drops were placed in test tube Number 25. After the salt solution was placed in the various tubes,

they were taken to the distilled-water burette, where as many drops of water were added as were needed to bring the total to a volume of 25 drops, e.g., Number 14 would receive 11 drops, while Number 25 would receive none. The contents in these tubes were thoroughly mixed by shaking. The percentage strength of the salt in any tube may then be found by multiplying its number by 0.02.

About 1 cc. of blood was drawn up with a clean dry syringe equipped with a small serum needle cut off so that it was only about 5 mm. in length. A drop was expelled immediately to each of the above-mentioned tubes, whose contents were then mixed by inverting.

The tubes stood two hours at room temperature before readings were made. At the end of this time the corpuscles had settled to the bottom, and hemolysis was indicated by the color of the supernatant fluid—faintly pink if hemolysis was partial and red, with little or no sediment, indicating complete hemolysis.

TEMPERATURE

The temperature of the guinea pigs was taken with a one-minute, clinical, Fahrenheit thermometer—10 cm. in length and with a mercury-bulb 1.5 cm. long. After lubricating the bulb well with vaseline it was passed into the rectum to 1.5 cm. The instrument was held in this position for three minutes before it was read.

Before considering my observations made on guinea pigs suffering from scurvy, it seems desirable to consider the blood counts made on normal guinea pigs by various investigators as given in Table I (p. 80). This table reveals the range of the counts made by different workers and gives the average of my counts on 35 normal guinea pigs. Except for the erythrocyte estimations of Cohnstein and Zuntz and of Malassez the agreement in the erythrocyte count is very good among the eight investigators and so is the estimation of hemoglobins of the four who made it. The leucocyte counts, on the other hand, vary greatly, and so do the differential counts.

Similar discrepancies are revealed in the summary given by Lucia '26, who found the eosinophile count only about half as high as my own although his lymphocyte count is somewhat higher.

The last number in each vertical column of Table II (p. 81) is an average count of all the first counts made by me on all the animals listed in Tables VIII and IX before these animals were placed on a deficient diet. Similar differences between the counts of different investigators are revealed in this table, but those in the white-cell counts are especially great, amounting to about 100 per cent in corresponding counts and over 700 per cent between minimum and maximum counts. The differences in the differential counts are greater still.

TABLE I*
BLOOD COUNTS ON NORMAL GUINEA PIGS BY VARIOUS INVESTIGATORS

Investigators	Temperature of Pig by Rectum	Erythrocytes per cmm.	Hemoglobin %	Leucocytes per cmm.	Poly-nuclear Leucocytes %	Lymphocytes, small and large %	Transitionals %	Large Mono-nuclears %	Eosinophiles %	Basophiles %
Bethe.....		5,144,000		7,240						
Cohnstein und Zuntz.....		4,240,000								
Hayem.....		5,859,500	93	5,600						
Kurloff.....		5,780,000		12,600	40.0 to 50.0	30.0 to 35.0		15.0 to 20.0	10.0	
Malassez.....		3,600,000								
Rieder.....				9,400						
Burnett.....		5,276,000	94.5	10,897	31.5	47.32		10.05	10.72	0.37
Goodall.....		5,600,000	100	9,170	37.0	60.0			3.0	
Eyre.....	38°62 C.									
Pembrey, Pitts, and Richet.....	37°4 C.									
McCormick.....	37°2 C.	4,960,000	99	6,097	26.0	65.1	1.5	3.2	3.7	
Lyons and Van de Carr....		5,565,000		9,600	34.9	49.0		7.0	3.1	0.8

* As far as I know, the "supra-vital" technique was used only by Lyons and Van de Carr.

TABLE II

MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM BLOOD COUNTS, ETC., ON NORMAL GUINEA PIGS BY DIFFERENT INVESTIGATORS

Investigators		Temperature	Erythrocytes	Hemoglobin	Leucocytes	Polynuclears	Lymphocytes	Mononuclears	Transitionals	Eosinophiles	Basophiles
S. H. Burnett.....	Min.		4,850,000	85%	5,555	18%	36%	7.2%	...	0.05%	0.18%
S. H. Burnett.....	Max.		6,000,000	100	21,895	41.28	59.5	15	...	20.3	0.87
S. H. Burnett.....	Av.		5,276,000	94.5	10,897	31.5	47.32	10.05	...	10.72	0.37
A. Goodall.....	Min.		4,800,000	90		21	42			6	
A. Goodall.....	Max.		6,880,000	120		52	71			8	
A. Goodall.....	Av.		5,600,000	100	9,170	37	60			3	
Eyre.....	Min.	36°0 C.									
Eyre.....	Max.	39°2 C.									
Eyre.....	Av.	38°62 C.									
Pembrey, Pitts, and Richet.....	Min.	36°0 C.									
Pembrey, Pitts, and Richet.....	Max.	40°2 C.									
Pembrey, Pitts, and Richet.....	Av.	*37°40 C.									
McCormick.....	Min.	36°3 C.	4,200,000	90	2,900	7.6	48.3	1.3	0	0	0
McCormick.....	Max.	38°0 C.	5,430,000	106	11,300	45.5	96.0	6.6	4.6	18.6	1.6
McCormick.....	Av.	37°2 C.	4,960,000	99	6,097	26.0	65.1	3.2	1.5	3.7	0.3

* Both averages were given in the original table.

Table III shows a variation in the number of leucocytes with the age (as indicated by weight) of the guinea pig after Gulland and Goodall. The white cells increase with weight, although the fluctuations in the individual counts are so great that this conclusion needs confirmation by a larger series of counts. Pig No. 1 when weighing 140 and 155 grams had larger counts, for example, than pig No. 4 when weighing 670 grams.

TABLE III
RELATION OF NUMBER OF LEUCOCYTES TO WEIGHT (OR AGE) IN FOUR NORMAL GUINEA PIGS (GULLAND AND GOODALL)

Pig No. 1		Pig No. 2		Pig No. 3		Pig No. 4	
Weight, Grams	Leucocytes per cmm.						
110.....	7,400	230.....	8,400	320.....	11,200	450.....	8,800
140.....	11,640	230.....	8,000	325.....	8,200	460.....	15,400
150.....	3,000	260.....	6,400	335.....	6,600	480.....	5,800
155.....	12,400	285.....	6,600	390.....	14,000	530.....	10,400
160.....	7,800	290.....	9,000	380.....	10,200	570.....	14,800
170.....	2,400			395.....	5,600	670.....	9,600
170.....	2,600					675.....	16,400
175.....	8,800					680.....	20,400
185.....	2,800					790.....	17,000
Average.....	6,537	Average.....	7,680	Average.....	9,300	Average.....	13,177

These compilations indicate that the counts of different investigators are in general agreement only, and that wide variations occur in the number of the various blood cells in normal guinea pigs, or that the methods are defective. My experience is in accordance with Goodall's '10 statement that blood counts in laboratory animals are apt to vary considerably.

Table IV gives the average first count on 35 normal pigs and the last counts on 27 scorbutic pigs, together with Groups I and IV of Series 2, used as controls. The excellent agreement between these counts is noteworthy. Those on the two groups (I and IV) of controls of Series 2 are in especially close agreement with the first readings on the animals of the other group. They also show that orange juice is a good substitute for the greens in so far as vitamine C is concerned. The effect of a deficient diet appears in the average last counts recorded in column two. These show a reduction in the erythrocyte count, an increase in the leucocyte count due to an absolute increase in the polymorphonuclears, and a decrease in the lymphocytes. They also show a decrease in hemoglobin, in the color index, and in temperature, an increase in reticulated and nucleated erythrocytes, and a so-called decrease in fragility.

I have given a digest of the estimations based on all of my counts and tests in Table V (p. 84) and Table VI (p. 86), which give a summary of the findings in Series 1 and 2, respectively. Since the first counts and lists were made before the animals were placed on a deficient diet they repre-

TABLE IV
SUMMARY TAKEN FROM TABLES VIII, IX, X, AND XI, SHOWING NORMAL AND FINAL VALUES OF BLOOD COMPONENTS IN THE GUINEA PIG

	Average for First Reading of S.1 and S.2 (Normal) Diet: Raw Alfalfa, Raw Barley, Greens, Water	Average for Last Reading of S.1, and Groups II and III, S.2. Diet: Raw Alfalfa, Raw Barley, and Water	Average for Group I, S.2 Diet: Raw Alfalfa, Raw Barley, Orange Juice, and Water	Average for Group IV, S.2 Diet: Raw Alfalfa, Raw Barley, Greens, Water
Erythrocytes.....	4,960,000	3,599,000	5,069,000	4,905,000
Leucocytes.....	6,097	10,032	6,133	5,010
Polymorphonuclears	26 per cent	55 per cent	16 per cent	25 per cent
Lymphocytes (small and large).....	64 per cent	33 per cent	75 per cent	68 per cent
Large Mononuclears.....	3 per cent	4 per cent	3 per cent	3 per cent
Eosinophiles.....	4.5 per cent	4 per cent	3 per cent	2 per cent
Basophiles.....	0.3 per cent	0.2 per cent	0.3 per cent	0.3 per cent
Transitionals.....	2 per cent	2 per cent	2 per cent	2 per cent
Hemoglobin.....	99 per cent	64 per cent	100 per cent	98 per cent
Color Index.....	1.0	0.89	0.99	0.99
Temperature.....	37°2 C.	35°2 C.	37°1 C.	37°0 C.
Reticulated Erythrocytes.....	1.0 per cent	14.9	1.0 per cent	2 per cent
Nucleated Erythrocytes.....	0	0.3 per cent	0	0
Hemolysis of Erythrocytes				
{ Began.....	0.44	0.40	0.43	0.43
{ Complete....	0.37	0.31	0.34	0.35
Weights.....	645	511	603	427

sent conditions in normal animals. Bold face figures indicate a decrease and those in roman type an increase. The figures recorded in these tables are percentages based on the initial and final readings except in case of the reticulated and nucleated erythrocytes, in which they represent the difference between the first and last readings in percentages.

Table VII (p. 88) is a summary from Tables V and VI, and shows that the temperature of the scorbutics fell an average of 3.2 per cent in all cases, while that of the normals increased 0.2 per cent, which probably is within

TABLE
SUMMARY OF RESULTS IN SERIES 1 RECORDED IN
[Bold face figures indicate

	Case Number									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Temperature.....	1.6	5.9	3.2	3.2	3.8	5.4	3.2	3.4	4.0	3.8
Erythrocytes.....	3.2	35.0	25.0	36.1	26.6	27.4	34.3	21.6	19.7	45.2
Hemoglobin.....	1.9	43.3	32.6	49.0	34.9	31.4	38.7	29.4	28.0	48.3
Color Index.....	1.0	11.0	1.0	17.0	10.0	10.0	7.2	13.6	4.0	5.6
Leucocytes.....	142.8	24.6	36.3	10.6	7.9	40.1	19.4	54.7	7.0	25.6
Differential Leucocyte Count										
Polymorphonuclears....	51.2	233.3	71.7	18.3	11.4	50.9	168.1	146.6	50.8	79.6
Lymphocytes, small and large.....	31.0	49.8	69.1	17.8	18.0	67.5	74.6	55.5	41.1	54.4
Eosinophiles.....	0	900.0	200.0	12.3	58.6	57.1	0	57.1	0	800.0
Basophiles.....	50.0	200.0	100.0	200.0	0	200.0	100.0	0	300.0	200.0
Mononuclears.....	50.0	53.3	257.1	78.5	75.0	38.4	675.0	114.2	22.2	44.4
Transitionals.....	0	300.0	166.6	0	500.0	78.5	2100.0	25.0	116.6	20.0
Reticulated Erythrocytes†....	0.7	14.4	7.2	38.9	32.1	26.6	24.0	19.0	11.3	27.2
Nucleated Erythrocytes†.....	0	0.3	0	0.4	0.2	0.3	0	0.1	0	0
Hemolysis of Erythrocytes										
Began.....	4.3	9.0	4.3	4.5	12.0	9.0	8.6	9.0	4.3	12.0
Complete.....	5.0	26.3	5.0	21.0	21.0	10.5	21.0	26.3	10.0	20.0
Loss in Weight.....	24.0	21.6	31.3	26.5	23.2	25.0	29.4	26.2	31.2	27.7

* Percentages calculated from the first and last readings in each "Case."

† Here the "difference" between the first and last readings in percentages is given.

the range of error. The erythrocytes of the scorbutics also fell in all cases, the average being 29.9 per cent, while those of the controls showed an average increase of 5.9 per cent. The hemoglobin of scorbutics likewise fell in all cases an average of 38.2 per cent, while that of controls rose an average of 1.6 per cent.

The color index of scorbutics was decreased in 96.6 per cent of the cases, it was increased in 1.6 per cent, and showed no change in 1.6 per cent. The average decrease was 12.2 per cent, while that of the controls showed an average decrease of only 3.3 per cent.

The leucocytes of scorbutics were decreased in 8.3 per cent of the cases and increased in 91.6 per cent, with an average increase of 79.8 per cent. Those of the controls were decreased in 12.5 per cent of the cases and increased in 87.5 per cent, with an average increase of 15.7 per cent. The polymorphonuclear leucocytes of scorbutics were decreased in 1.6 per cent of the cases and increased in 98.3 per cent, with an average increase of 232.6 per cent. Those of controls showed an average increase of only 2.4

V

PERCENTAGES BASED ON INITIAL AND FINAL READINGS*

decrease; roman, increase]

Case Number										Average	Cases Decrease %	Cases Increase %	Cases No Change %
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20				
3.8	2.4	4.2	3.4	4.0	4.0	4.4	1.4	0.6	2.7	3.4	100	0	0
27.9	17.8	15.8	23.1	34.3	24.4	23.0	2.2	29.9	23.7	24.8	100	0	0
42.0	25.5	5.8	32.6	46.1	35.7	37.7	1.0	37.3	28.7	31.4	100	0	0
18.0	7.0	1.0	13.4	18.0	11.1	17.0	0	10.4	6.1	9.1	90	5	5
49.2	111.0	88.2	63.2	186.3	115.4	21.1	5.4	52.9	160.7	48.0	25	75	0
166.0	69.6	211.1	282.3	38.8	167.6	162.4	108.0	88.0	72.0	114.7	5	95	0
24.0	51.4	45.6	65.0	72.0	85.3	60.9	32.8	19.1	29.0	42.4	95	5	0
134.7	235.3	88.8	50.0	100.0	500.0	16.2	59.3	100.0	0	90.3	35	45	20
100.0	200.0	0	0	600.0	200.0	0	0	0	0	47.5	25	35	40
0	5.2	166.6	66.6	0	66.6	20.0	57.1	0	175.0	81.8	15	70	15
57.1	100.0	60.0	66.6	50.0	0	60.0	40.0	0	33.3	150.7	35	45	20
38.8	12.4	8.0	16.4	13.7	10.7	17.6	2.3	1.5	1.5	15.9	0	100	0
1.1	0.5	0.6	0.1	1.6	0.1	0	0	0	0.1	0.2	0	60	40
9.0	8.6	0	12.0	9.0	13.6	9.0	0	4.7	9.5	7.6	90	0	10
22.2	21.0	15.7	21.0	26.3	26.3	31.5	0	11.1	16.6	17.8	95	0	5
29.4	19.3	28.2	45.7	38.4	21.8	30.2	31.6	8.1	18.3	26.8	100	0	0

per cent. The lymphocytes (small and large) of the scorbutic pigs were decreased in 98.3 per cent of the cases and increased in 1.6 per cent, with an average decrease of 63.7 per cent.

The eosinophiles of scorbutics were decreased in 31.1 per cent of the cases and increased in 51.1 per cent. They showed no change in 17.1 per cent of the cases, with an average increase of 37.6 per cent. In the controls they suffered a decrease in 62.5 per cent of the cases, an increase in 37.5 per cent, with an average increase of 12.9 per cent.

The basophiles of the scorbutics showed a decrease in 27.7 per cent of the cases, an increase in 33.8 per cent, and no change in 38.3 per cent, with an average increase of 44.6 per cent. Those of the controls showed an average decrease of 0.8 per cent.

The monocytes of scorbutics showed a decrease in 32.7 per cent of the cases and an increase in 51.1 per cent. There was no change in 16.1 per cent of the cases. The average increase was 18.3 per cent. In controls there was a decrease in 62.5 per cent of the cases and an increase in 37.5 per cent, with an average decrease of 16.8 per cent.

The transitionals of scorbutics decreased in 42.2 per cent of the cases,

TABLE
SUMMARY OF CHANGES IN SERIES 2 IN PERCENT
[Bold face figures indicate

	Group I				Av.	
	Case Number					
	1	2	3	4		
Temperature.....	1.0	0.6	0	0.2	.8	
Erythrocytes.....	3.1	2.6	2.8	2.5	.2	
Hemoglobin.....	2.0	1.9	2.2	2.0	.0	
Color Index.....	0	1.0	2.0	0	.2	
Leucocytes.....	6.4	4.5	5.8	8.0	2.9	
Differential Leucocyte Count	Polymorphonuclears.....	16.0	7.3	28.9	16.2	1.0
	Lymphocytes, small and large.....	3.9	10.0	11.4	3.1	5.1
	Eosinophiles.....	33.3	50.0	80.0	60.0	14.1
	Basophiles.....	100.0	200.0	40.0	66.6	1.6
	Mononuclears.....	27.2	54.5	46.1	41.4	15.0
	Transitionals.....	150.0	62.5	16.6	14.2	22.4
Reticulated Erythrocytes.....	0.1	0.4	0.8	0.2	.2	
Nucleated Erythrocytes.....	0	0	0	0	0	
Hemolysis of Erythrocytes	{ Began.....	0	0	0	0	
	{ Complete.....	0	0	0	5.5	1.3
Change in weight.....	12.2	9.8	65.5	15.8	25.8	

* Percentages calculated from the first and last readings in each "Case."

† This animal was killed for study of early pathological changes not concerned with the experiment.

‡ Here the "difference" between the first and last readings in percentages is given.

increased in 40.0 per cent, and showed no change in 17.7 per cent. The average increase was 77.0 per cent. Those of the controls were decreased in 50 per cent of the cases and increased in 50 per cent, with an average increase of 41.7 per cent.

The reticulated erythrocytes of scorbutics showed an increase in 100 per cent of the cases, with an average increase of 13.0 per cent. Those of controls suffered an average decrease of 0.5 per cent. The nucleated erythrocytes of scorbutics were increased in 78.3 per cent of the cases, showed no change in 21.6 per cent, with an average increase of 0.3 per cent. Those of controls showed no change in all cases.

Hemolysis began later in the scorbutics in 88.3 per cent of the cases. There was no change in 11.6 per cent. The average decrease was 8.4 per cent. In the controls the average increase was 0.5 per cent. The completion of hemolysis was hastened in 81.6 per cent of the scorbutic animals. No change was established in 18.3 per cent of the cases, and the average de-

VI

TAGES BASED ON INITIAL AND FINAL READINGS*

decrease; roman, increase]

Group II					Group III					Group IV				
Case Number				Av.	Case Number				Av.	Case Number				Av.
5	6	7	8		9	10	11†	12		13	14	15	16	
4.0	2.2	3.6	3.2	3.2	3.8	3.4		2.4	3.2	0.8	0.4	0.2	0.4	.2
40.8	40.0	38.8	5.9	31.3	44.0	20.1		36.9	33.6	7.1	22.5	4.4	18.0	11.7
49.5	49.0	51.9	9.8	40.0	49.5	41.8		38.8	43.3	3.0	8.6	3.0	4.2	3.2
14.0	15.3	24.0	8.0	15.3	9.4	25.0		3.0	12.4	2.0	10.9	4.0	9.0	6.4
233.9	135.2	68.0	61.7	124.7	124.0	75.3		16.6	71.9	12.0	30.7	44.0	27.5	28.5
434.1	107.0	315.2	281.5	284.4	42.2	158.4		695.6	298.7	12.2	6.6	2.0	20.0	5.9
267.6	48.3	60.5	57.9	108.5	21.3	35.4		63.9	40.2	2.4	11.6	7.6	4.7	.7
25.0	25.8	50.0	65.3	8.8	66.6	25.0		0	13.8	30.0	10.0	250.0	50.0	40.0
0	50.0	0	0	12.5	200.0	100.0		200.0	100.0	0	100.0	200.0	100.0	0
33.3	10.0	0	45.0	17.0	7.6	0		37.5	9.9	8.3	30.7	137.5	40.0	18.7
25.0	50.0	300.0	42.8	91.9	20.0	14.2		0	11.4	66.6	14.2	25.0	300.0	61.0
5.3	11.4	25.9	1.3	10.9	11.3	22.0		3.6	12.3	0.1	1.2	2.1	0.3	.8
0.7	0.9	0.2	0	.4	0.2	0.7		0.1	.3	0	0	0	0	0
9.5	9.0	9.5	0	7.0	13.0	10.5		9.0	10.8	0	0	4.7	0	1.1
0	16.6	16.5	0	8.2	20.0	16.6		17.6	18.0	0	0	0	0	0
31.0	19.1	26.2	31.5	26.9	30.0	31.6		27.9	29.8	36.0	133.3	58.4	91.7	79.8

crease was 14.6 per cent. An average increase of 0.6 per cent was observed in controls.

This summary shows very distinct changes in the blood picture in scorbutic pigs, except perhaps in regard to the transitionals, monocytes, basophiles, and eosinophiles.

There was a loss in weight in 100 per cent of the scorbutic pigs, the average decrease being 27.8 per cent. (See Table VII.) The controls, on the other hand, all gained weight, the average increase having been 52.8 per cent.

Hess '20 stated that a low-grade fever (100-101) frequently accompanies scurvy in man, but noted that it may not be a true "scorbutic fever" but merely a "condition grafted upon the nutritional disturbance," for it sharply subsides upon the giving of antiscorbutic food. Hess attributed the high temperature to a complicating infection. Whatever the explanation may be, no rise in temperature was noted at any time in these or in any other animals except when antiscorbutic food was given. Hence my results confirm the conclusion of Jackson and Moore '16 that "there is likewise no rise in temperature during the disease" [experimental scurvy]

TABLE VII

SUMMARY MADE FROM TABLES V AND VI, SHOWING PERCENTAGE CHANGES IN THE NORMAL CONTROLS AND SCORBUTICS

[In columns showing average change bold face figures indicate decrease; roman, increase]

	Normal Controls*				Scorbutics†				
	Average Change	Percentage Cases Decrease	Percentage Cases Increase	Percentage Cases No Change	Average Change	Percentage Cases Decrease	Percentage Cases Increase	Percentage Cases No Change	
Temperature.....	0.2	25	62.5	12.5	3.2	100	0	0	
Erythrocytes.....	5.9	25	75	0	29.9	100	0	0	
Hemoglobin.....	1.6	37.5	62.5	0	38.2	100	0	0	
Color Index.....	3.3	62.5	12.5	25	12.2	96.6	1.6	1.6	
Leucocytes.....	15.7	12.5	87.5	0	79.8	8.3	91.6	0	
Differential Leucocyte Count	Polymorphonuclears.....	2.4	50	50	0	232.6	1.6	98.3	0
	Lymphocytes, small and large.....	2.2	50	50	0	63.7	98.3	1.6	0
	Eosinophiles.....	12.9	62.5	37.5	0	37.6	81.1	51.1	17.1
	Basophiles.....	0.8	62.5	25	12.5	44.6	27.7	33.8	38.3
	Mononuclears.....	16.8	62.5	37.5	0	18.3	22.7	51.1	16.1
	Transitionals.....	41.7	50	50	0	77.0	42.2	40.0	17.7
Reticulated Erythrocytes.....	0.5	75	25	0	13.0	0	100	0	
Nucleated Erythrocytes.....	0	0	0	100	0.3	0	78.3	21.6	
Hemolysis of Erythrocytes	Began.....	0.5	0	12.5	87.5	8.4	88.3	0	11.6
	Complete.....	0.6	0	12.5	87.5	14.6	81.6	0	18.3
Change in Weight.....	52.8	0	100	0	27.8	100	0	0	

* Groups I and IV, Series 2.

† Series 1, and Groups II and III, Series 2.

in guinea pigs, although a majority of the scorbutic pigs showed a moderate leucocytosis. Since this leucocytosis very quickly ends upon the resumption of antiscorbutic feeding, it seems unlikely that it is due to infection, although weakened scorbutic animals well may be more susceptible to it.

Gulland and Goodall '25 suggested that "the leucocytes, owing to the hemorrhages, are generally found to be increased, but in the absence of recent hemorrhage . . . they are diminished."

It is apparent from my counts that the polymorphonuclear leucocytes and lymphocytes vary inversely with each other. This is represented in Figure VIII.

It should be noted that the only animal (Case 4, Series 1) with a lymphocytosis had a decrease in polymorphonuclears. It is possible that this pig was not normal at the beginning and the conflicting statements in regard to leucocytosis and leucopenia may be due to failure on the part of some investigators to recognize this fact. Changes in leucocyte count are due to changes in the lymphocyte and polymorphonuclear counts to the extent of 90 per cent, the remainder being due to changes in monocytes, eosinophiles, basophiles, and transitionals, but the changes in the eosinophiles, basophiles, monocytes, and transitional cells do not seem to be characteristic. Since the erythrocyte count, the hemoglobin, and the color index decreased consistently, one may conclude that these changes in cell count are due to the deficient diet. (See Figure VI.) The hemoglobin decreased proportionately more than the erythrocytes. (See Table VII.) This agrees with the findings of Eichhorst in man, and of Liotta in guinea pigs.

The decrease in red blood cells may reflect either increased blood destruction or decreased production. Since smears of the bone marrow show the presence of an increased number of nucleated reds as compared to normals, it seems that there is an increased blood destruction and stimulation of the marrow, although it may also mean that the erythrocytes enter the blood sooner.

The reticulated cells increased 13 per cent in scorbutic pigs, while in the non-scorbutic the average decrease was 0.5 per cent. This increase in reticulated cells may be considered as indicating an entry of younger cells into the circulation. As shown in Figure VII, they began to appear after about three weeks' feeding of the deficient diet. Smears made from the bone marrow failed to show the presence of reticulated cells nor could the very large red cells be found. Blood smears from the same blood, made at the same time, and stained for leucocytes with Jenner and Giemsa and with Unna's solution for reticulated erythrocytes, revealed large vacuolated red cells, which were found to be the reticulated forms. (See Figures I

and III.²) Many nucleated erythrocytes could be observed on the bone marrow smears. It would also seem that, whatever the cause of red-cell destruction, the young cells are more susceptible to its influence. This would imply a drop in the erythrocyte count and this is what was found in these experiments. Since I was able to predict the presence of extensive hemorrhages from the red-cell count, or from an estimation of hemoglobin, hemorrhage seems the most likely cause for this destruction.

The increase in nucleated reds in the great majority of cases of scorbutics may be due to an increased activity in the bone marrow as shown by the increase in the nucleated red cells there. As shown in Figures II and VII, nucleated reds appear relatively later in the circulation—about the fourth week of feeding—than do the reticulated cells.

My observations on fragility of erythrocytes are in accord with those of other workers (Hess '20) on the same animal. I found a slight decrease in fragility after about two weeks. (See Figure V.)

It seems to be a rule that the concentration necessary for hemolysis drops with the hemoglobin and the red-cell count. This is shown in Figures V, VI, IX. In Case 1, Series 1 (Table VIII pp. 94–97) for example, neither the hemoglobin nor red-cell count showed any appreciable change, nor did the fragility test. The sudden drop of hemoglobin within the cell may leave a correspondingly lower tension. Hence a lower concentration of saline solution will be necessary to maintain the initial osmotic gradient and to equalize this gradient and so complete hemolysis. The synchronous drop of fragility with hemoglobin suggests the dependence of the former upon the latter. I can confirm the statement of Hess '20 that "the red cells show poikilocytosis and anisocytosis" as illustrated in Figure I. Many cases seem to show a greater tendency toward crenation as the scurvy progresses.

Hess stated that "guinea pigs generally die of scurvy after having lost about one-third of their body weight; occasionally the loss is greater, reaching almost 50 per cent." My results are in general agreement with these. The average loss of weight in scorbutic guinea pigs was 27.8 per cent. (See Table XIV p. 105.) I found that loss in weight began about the twenty-second day of feeding (see Figures IV and IX) but the slight increase in weight in the early stages of the experiment is considerably less than would be expected in normal animals.

All of these scorbutic guinea pigs died after a period of 25 to 44 days, an average of 35.9 days. With a very few exceptions the uniformity of duration is surprising (see Table XII, p. 104, and Table XIII, p. 105). This implies a uniformity in the animals, in the conditions, and in freedom from outside influence and infection.

² Figures I–III appear as Plate I immediately following the text.

FIG. IV.—Graphs of weight and rectal temperature of all scorbutic animals.

FIG. V.—Graphs showing the beginning and end of hemolysis at different intervals in the experiment.

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FIG. VI.—Graphs showing changes in the red-cell count, the percentage of hemoglobin, and the color index.

FIG. VII.—Graphs representing the percentage of nucleated and reticulated erythrocytes.

FIG. VIII.—Graphs based upon the number of leucocytes per cubic millimeter and upon the number of lymphocytes and polymorphonuclears in three hundred leucocytes.

FIG. IX.—A reproduction of all the graphs of Figures IV–VIII, inclusive. Graph 1 represents weight; 2, temperature; 3, beginning of hemolysis; 4, completion of hemolysis; 5, erythrocyte count; 6, hemoglobin; 7, color index; 8, nucleated erythrocytes; 9, reticulated erythrocytes; 10, lymphocytes (small and large); 11, polymorphonuclears; and 12, total leucocyte count per cubic millimeter.

TABLE VIII
BLOOD COUNTS OF SERIES 1 GUINEA PIGS WITH SCURVY

Case	Sex	Date	Time	Temperature†	Erythrocytes‡	Hemoglobins	Color Index	Leucocytes	Differential Count§					Reticulated Erythrocytes¶	Nucleated Erythrocytes**	Fragility		
									Polymorphonuclears	Lymphocytes	Eosinophiles	Basophiles	Mononuclears			Transitionals	Began	Complete
*1.....	F	1926																
		3-29	3:00	100	5,260,000	102	.99	4,900	60	219	2	2	12	5	% .5	0	.46	.40
		4-17	10:25	99.4	5,350,000	102	.95	4,500	44	240	1	0	10	4	.4	0	.44	.38
		4-24	11:00	98.4	5,070,000	100	.99	8,200	45	247	1	0	2	5	.9	0	.44	.38
		4-29	10:15	98.6	4,880,000	98	1.0	9,600	116	154	4	2	18	6	.9	0	.44	.38
5-5	10:20	98.4	5,090,000	100	1.0	11,900	123	151	2	1	18	5	1.2	0	.44	.38		
2.....	F	4-7			5,300,000	106	1.0	7,300	42	239	2	2	15	0	.5	0	.44	.38
		4-17	1:10	100.2	5,400,000	105	.97	4,900	68	211	10	1	7	3	.4	0	.44	.38
		4-24	2:40	98.6	4,980,000	98	.99	6,600	67	177	36	1	15	4	.4	0	.44	.38
		4-28	2:10	97.8	4,660,000	95	1.0	5,900	80	185	20	0	10	5	1.9	0	.44	.38
		5-7	12:20	96	4,420,000	89	1.0	6,000	138	116	26	2	10	8	2.0	0	.44	.38
5-11	10:45	94.2	3,440,000	60	.89	5,500	140	130	20	0	7	3	15.9	0.3	.40	.28		
3.....	F	4-8		98.6	5,140,000	101	.99	6,300	54	233	2	1	7	3		0	.46	.40
		4-17	2:30	98.6	5,370,000	103	.96	4,600	47	243	1	0	4	5	.3	0	.46	.40
		4-23	3:30	98.4	5,170,000	101	.98	7,100	52	224	6	0	11	7	.4	0	.46	.40
		4-29	4:30	98.4	4,840,000	90	.93	8,900	48	227	4	0	11	10	.3	0	.46	.40
		5-7	1:55	95.4	3,900,000	68	.89	9,900	191	70	6	0	25	8	7.5	0	.44	.38
4.....	F	4-8		98.6	4,790,000	100	1.0	10,300	136	112	33	2	14	3	0	0	.44	.38
		4-12	4:00	100.4	5,260,000	102	.97	4,300	47	217	24	0	10	2	0.3	0	.44	.38
		4-23	4:15	98.6	5,060,000	99	.98	5,200	43	226	20	0	10	1	0.4	0	.44	.38
		4-29	4:30	98.4	4,460,000	...		6,000	92	158	24	0	23	3	1.3	0	.44	.38
		5-8	3:20	97.2	3,790,000	67	.89	8,500	122	116	25	0	27	10	10.1	0	.42	.32
		5-10	1:20	95.4	3,060,000	51	.83	11,400	111	132	29	0	25	3	34.2	0.4	.42	.30

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5.....	F	4-8	1:30	98.6	5,100,000	108	1.00	11,800	96	177	22	0	4	1		0	.46	.38
		4-19	2:06	98.4	5,210,000	108	.99	7,800	78	163	33	3	17	5	0.2	0	.44	.38
		4-24	3:00	98.6	4,920,000	100	1.0	9,100	57	198	31	1	11	2	0.0	0	.44	.38
		4-28	3:00	99.2	4,480,000	98	1.1	11,600	70	185	30	0	11	4	0.9	0	.44	.38
		5-8	9:20	96.6	4,010,000	98	1.1	12,500	102	121	48	0	15	14	7.1	0	.44	.38
		5-13	12:40	94.8	3,740,000	67	.90	10,400	107	145	35	0	7	6	32.3	0.2	.40	.30
6.....	M	4-8	1:00	100	5,140,000	105	1.0	6,700	80	184	7	2	13	14	0.0	0	.44	.38
		4-19	12:00	99.2	5,170,000	100	.97	5,100	60	221	7	1	8	3	0.0	0	.44	.38
		4-24	1:15	98.6	4,910,000	97	.98	5,500	96	192	3	0	7	2	0.7	0	.44	.38
		4-29	11:00	98.0	4,960,000	97	.97	5,900	164	113	6	0	12	5	1.8	0	.42	.38
		5-6	10:00	96.6	5,150,000	98	.95	6,500	61	221	3	0	8	7	2.4	0	.44	.38
		5-11	1:50	95	4,080,000	72	.90	13,800	153	129	0	2	7	9	3.6	0.1	.40	.34
5-13	11:00	94.6	3,730,000	...		11,200	163	109	3	4	18	3	26.6	0.3	...	...		
7.....	F	4-10	12:00	98.8	5,120,000	98	.96	7,700	66	214	16	0	4	0	0.0	0	.46	.38
		4-19	4:00	99.2	4,990,000	101	1.0	5,800	112	159	20	0	3	6	0.0	0	.44	.38
		4-26	3:15	99	4,100,000	92	1.1	5,900	119	137	32	1	6	5	0.8	0	.44	.38
		5-5	4:20	98.4	3,960,000	73	.92	6,400	129	89	70	1	10	1	3.0	0	...	...
		5-12	3:50	95.6	3,360,000	60	.89	6,200	177	54	16	1	31	21	24.0	0	.42	.30
8.....	F	4-10	1:20	97.4	5,370,000	102	.95	7,300	75	207	7	0	7	4	0	0	.44	.38
		4-19	4:30	98	5,340,000	103	.97	5,900	28	252	10	1	4	5	0.2	0	.44	.38
		4-26	4:45	99	4,830,000	99	1.0	6,300	58	184	32	0	22	4	0.1	0	.44	.38
		5-6	3:15	96.6		...			115	99	29	0	32	25		0	.44	.38
		5-9	1:30	94	4,210,000	72	.82	11,300	185	92	3	0	15	5	19.0	0.1	.40	.28
9.....	F	4-13	1:20	98.6	4,720,000	100	1.0	5,400	112	168	4	1	9	6	0.0	0	.46	.40
		4-20	11:45	99.2	5,050,000	99	.98	6,100	109	175	3	0	8	5	0.0	0	.46	.38
		4-26	11:20	99	4,120,000	86	1.0	4,200	118	167	2	2	10	1	0.7	0	.46	.38
		4-30	11:30	98	4,320,000	...		4,700	151	123	3	1	11	6	1.0	0	.46	.38
		5-4	12:25	97	3,860,000	73	.99	4,700	155	102	0	2	22	19	7.4	0.1	...	...
		5-5	12:20	94.6	3,790,000	72	.96	5,000	169	99	4	4	11	13	11.3	0	.44	.36

* First reading in each case.

† By rectum-clinical centigrade thermometer.

‡ Certified Leitz Hemacytometer, Double Neubauer Counting Chamber, and Thoma's Blood Diluting Pipettes.

§ Sahli-Leitz Nonfade Hemometer—percentage of Hemoglobin read off directly.

|| Smears stained by the Jenner-Giemsa Method and three hundred leucocytes counted.

¶ By Widal-Abrami and Brule Method. One thousand erythrocytes counted.

** One thousand erythrocyte cells counted for nucleated cells. Jenner-Giemsa stain used.

TABLE VIII—Continued*
BLOOD COUNTS OF SERIES 1 GUINEA PIGS WITH SCURVY

Case	Sex	Date	Time	Temperature	Erythrocytes	Hemoglobin§	Color Index	Leucocytes	Differential Count						Reticulated Erythrocytes¶	Nucleated Erythrocytes**	Fragility	
									Polymorphonuclears	Lymphocytes	Eosinophiles	Basophiles	Mononuclears	Transitionals			Began	Complete
10.....	F	1926																
		4-13	5:00	98.6	5,240,000	98	.89	7,200	118	156	8	0	13	5	%	%	%	%
		4-20	11:45	99	5,250,000	100	.95	5,400	91	183	6	0	12	8		0	.46	.40
		4-26	1:20	99.2	4,530,000	87	.96	4,700	76	183	17	2	16	6	0.8	0	.46	.40
		4-30	12:30	99	4,700,000	...		6,200	38	232	6	0	22	2	0.7	0	.46	.40
		5-6	12:45	96.6	4,300,000	77	.89	7,800	104	168	6	1	18	3	0.9	0	.46	.40
		5-12	5:10	94.8	2,870,000	48	.84	5,800	212	71	0	2	9	1.7	0	.46	.40	
														28.0	0	.40	.32	
11.....	M	4-14	10:00	98.6	4,860,000	100	1.0	6,700	71	191	23	0	8	7	0.4	0	.44	.36
		4-21	11:00	99	4,450,000	100	1.1	6,400	67	190	27	1	7	8	0.3	0	.44	.38
		4-27	10:20	99.2	4,490,000	101	1.1	7,700	69	190	31	1	5	4	0.7	0	.44	.38
		5-3	10:40	98.2	4,630,000	98	1.0	13,100	98	166	23	2	5	1	0.5	0	.44	.38
		5-8	10:00	99	4,400,000	91	1.0	12,600	148	91	42	5	9	5	6.6	0	.42	.36
		5-10	5:00	95.2	3,590,000	67	.94	7,400	196	66	18	0	12	8	27.0	0.3	.40	.28
		5-12	12:40	94.8	3,500,000	58	.82	13,200	189	45	54	1	8	3	39.2	1.1	...	...
12.....	F	4-14	11:30	98.6	4,750,000	98	1.0	6,800	102	167	3	2	19	7	0.5	0	.46	.38
		4-21	1:00	99	5,260,000	100	.95	5,500	110	159	3	0	20	8	0.3	0	.46	.38
		4-27	11:00	98	4,920,000	97	.97	7,400	122	139	4	1	23	6	1.0	0	.46	.38
		5-3	11:20	98.8	4,700,000	97	1.0	7,000	138	142	2	1	13	4	3.2	0.1	.44	.36
		5-8	1:15	96.2	3,900,000	73	.93	13,400	173	81	10	0	20	14	12.9	0.5	.42	.30
13.....	F	4-14	4:00	98.2	5,400,000	103	.95	4,200	54	216	9	0	6	5	0.6	0	.44	.38
		4-21	2:45	98.4	5,010,000	100	1.0	6,800	51	225	10	1	7	6	0.4	0	.44	.38
		4-27	2:15	99.2	4,950,000	98	.99	5,600	83	202	8	0	4	3	0.7	0	.44	.38
		5-5	3:00	99	5,170,000	97	.94	8,000	154	123	1	1	14	7	8.6	0	.44	.32
		5-9	11:45	94	4,550,000	...			168	113	1	0	16	2		0.6	...	...

* See footnotes on page 95.

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14.....	M	4-14	5:00	98.4	5,220,000	101	.97	6,800	51	232	8	0	6	3	0.8	0	.46	.38
		4-21	4:45	98.2	5,020,000	102	1.0	6,800	43	243	7	1	4	2	0.4	0	.46	.38
		4-27	5:00	99	5,000,000	101	1.1	10,200	85	171	30	1	11	2	0.5	0	...	...
		5-6	5:00	98.4	5,620,000	103	.91	12,100	110	106	47	2	25	10	1.1	0	.46	.36
		5-13	4:35	95	4,010,000	68	.85	11,100	195	81	4	0	15	5	17.2	0.1	.40	.30
15.....	M	4-15	12:45	98.8	5,210,000	104	1.0	5,500	50	243	1	0	4	2	0.2	0	.44	.38
		4-22	12:50	98.6	5,200,000	101	.97	7,700	56	231	0	1	7	5	0.3	0	.44	.38
		4-27	3:55	98	4,570,000	95	1.0	9,600	121	163	1	0	10	5	0.2	0.1	.44	.38
		5-4	2:15	97.8	4,480,000	88	.98	7,100	200	87	0	0	11	2	0.7	0	.44	.36
		5-11	5:20	98	3,410,000	56	.82	13,000	231	47	2	0	16	4	2.8	0.2	.40	.28
		5-13	2:30	94.8	3,220,000	...			219	68	2	6	4	1	13.9	1.6	...	...
16.....	F	4-15	2:00	98.6	4,980,000	98	.99	7,100	99	184	5	1	9	2	0.6	0	.44	.38
		4-22	1:30	99	5,270,000	102	.97	6,900	87	201	2	0	7	3	0.2	0	.44	.38
		4-28	1:30	99.2	4,960,000	101	1.0	7,100	87	201	3	0	8	1	1.4	0	.44	.38
		5-4	3:45	98	4,730,000	98	1.0	7,200	120	156	2	0	20	2	3.1	0	.44	.38
		5-11	9:30	94.6	3,550,000	63	.88	15,300	265	27	0	3	3	2	11.3	0.1	.38	.28
17.....	F	4-16	9:45	98.8	4,770,000	98	1.0	5,200	69	182	37	2	5	5	0.2	0	.44	.38
		4-23	11:15	99	5,290,000	102	.97	5,600	76	167	42	0	14	1	0.3	0	.44	.38
		4-28	10:24	99.4	5,090,000	102	1.0	4,600	54	197	35	0	11	3	0.0	0	.44	.38
		5-4	9:00	97.6	4,850,000	96	.98	7,500	122	99	65	1	13	0	0.3	0	.42	.36
		5-12	1:20	94.4	3,670,000	61	.83	6,300	188	71	31	2	6	2	17.8	0	.40	.26
18.....	F	4-16	11:30	98.6	4,380,000	100	1.0	5,500	49	225	13	1	7	5	0.0	0	.44	.38
		4-23	11:45	98.4	5,170,000	101	.98	5,600	41	227	20	0	6	6	0.0	0	.44	.38
		4-28	11:00	98.2	4,880,000	94	.96	6,800	70	199	17	0	10	4	0.1	0	.44	.38
		5-4	9:45	97.2	4,770,000	99	1.0	5,800	102	151	32	1	11	3	2.3	0	.44	.38
19.....	F	4-16	2:00	99.2	5,150,000	99	.96	4,200	53	234	0	0	6	7	1.3	0	.42	.36
		4-22	4:00	99	5,210,000	100	.96	5,300	66	225	1	0	3	5	0.9	0	.42	.36
		4-28	2:50	99.2	4,050,000	83	.91	4,000	59	228	2	0	8	3	1.5	0	.42	.36
		4-30	2:30	98.8	4,390,000	...		5,800	60	223	0	0	9	8	1.7	0	...	...
		5-31†	3:20	98.6	3,610,000	62	.86	6,500	97	189	1	0	6	7	3.3	0	.40	.32
		5-8	4:00	97.2	3,340,000	61	.80	5,300	176	111	1	0	7	5	14.3	0	.38	.30
5-24	10:00	98.6	5,320,000	94	.88	5,400	158	128	0	0	5	9		0	.42	.36		
20.....	F	4-16	3:00	100.4	4,320,000	94	.97	4,200	86	207	0	0	4	3	1.0	0	.42	.36
		4-22	4:30	99	5,100,000	100	.98	5,000	101	186	2	0	7	4	1.3	0	.42	.36
		4-28	3:30	99	4,100,000	78	.95	5,400	126	158	3	0	9	4	1.1	0	.42	.36
		4-30	2:30	97.8	3,920,000	...		5,600	168	109	2	0	16	5	1.2	0	...	...
		5-31†	3:20	97.6	3,680,000	67	.91	10,900	138	147	0	0	11	4	2.5	0.1	.38	.30
		5-8	5:20	98	4,660,000	72	.77	5,300	143	146	2	0	9	0	8.1	0.2	.38	.30
		5-24	11:30	98.4	5,230,000	99	.95	5,600	131	154	4	0	6	5		0	.42	.36

†† Lettuce added to the diet, 5:00 P.M., May 4, 1926.

TABLE IX

BLOOD COUNTS OF SERIES 2 GUINEA PIGS WITH SCURVY

Case	Sex	Date	Time	Temperature	Erythrocytes	Hemoglobin	Color Index	Leucocytes	Differential Count						Reticulated Erythrocytes	Nucleated Erythrocytes	Fragility	
									Polymorphonuclears	Lymphocytes	Eosinophiles	Basophiles	Mononuclears	Transitionals			Began	Complete
1.....	F	1926																
		6-10	10:35	98	4,720,000	98	1.0	7,800	50	233	3	1	11	2	%	0	%	%
		6-18	11:05	98.6	4,980,000	98	.99	8,000	47	222	0	0	20	11	.4	0	.42	.36
		6-25	10:25	99	5,360,000	103	.96	7,600	61	210	11	2	9	7	.4	0	.42	.36
		7-1	9:00	98.6	5,170,000	101	.98	8,100	38	238	3	3	7	6	.3	0	.42	.36
		7-6	8:50	99	4,860,000	99	1.0	7,700	73	198	9	0	13	7	.5	0	.42	.36
		7-12	9:00	98.6	4,940,000	101	1.0	6,300	64	209	3	0	16	8	.3	0	.40	.36
		7-16	8:45	99	5,250,000	103	.97	6,700	78	197	10	1	11	3	.2	0	.42	.36
		7-24	12:30	99	4,870,000	100	1.0	7,300	58	224	4	0	9	5	.4	0	.42	.36
2.....	F	6-10	10:35	98	5,350,000	102	.95	6,600	68	180	32	1	11	8	.7	0	.44	.36
		6-18	11:30	98.8	5,260,000	102	.97	6,100	37	224	17	2	12	8	.6	0	.42	.36
		6-25	11:00	99	5,230,000	101	.97	5,700	43	223	23	0	9	2	.8	0	.44	.36
		7-1	10:00	99.2	4,950,000	98	.99	5,600	61	208	16	0	8	7	1.1	0	.44	.36
		7-6	9:30	98.8	5,200,000	101	.97	6,300	48	224	13	0	11	4	.7	0	.44	.36
		7-12	10:30	99	5,020,000	100	1.0	5,700	52	212	27	2	7	0	1.0	0	.44	.36
		7-16	10:00	99	5,000,000	98	.98	6,400	45	223	19	4	6	3	.9	0	.44	.34
		7-24	1:30	98.6	5,210,000	100	.96	6,900	63	198	16	3	17	3	1.1	0	.44	.36
		3.....	F	6-11	11:30	99	4,300,000	90	1.0	5,100	38	228	10	5	13	6	2.9	0
6-18	2:15			99	4,330,000	90	1.0	4,700	51	230	5	2	8	4	2.6	0	.44	.34
6-25	1:15			98.8	4,790,000	93	.97	6,300	44	231	3	0	11	11	1.9	0	.44	.34
7-1	11:30			98.8	4,730,000	92	.96	5,000	35	241	7	0	14	3	2.0	0	.44	.34
7-6	11:05			99.2	4,660,000	92	.98	4,920	38	233	13	1	8	7	1.7	0	.44	.34
7-12	12:30			99	4,670,000	93	1.0	4,780	62	214	6	0	10	8	2.3	0	.44	.34
7-16	10:30			98.6	4,800,000	93	.97	4,700	40	237	1	3	9	10	.9	0	.44	.32
7-24	9:00			99	4,720,000	92	.98	5,400	27	254	2	3	7	7	2.1	0	.44	.34

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4.....	F	6-12	11:45	99.2	5,100,000	99	.97	5,000	43	225	5	3	17	7	.9	0	.44	.36
		6-18	3:00	98.8	4,980,000	96	.98	5,400	48	238	0	0	11	3	.7	0	.44	.36
		6-25	2:30	99	5,060,000	99	.98	6,100	61	226	2	0	8	3	1.0	0	.44	.36
		7-1	1:10	98.6	5,000,000	98	.98	5,800	40	236	2	2	11	9	.5	0	.44	.36
		7-6	12:00	99	4,900,000	95	.96	6,200	39	242	4	0	7	8	.8	0	.42	.36
		7-12	12:50	98.8	5,016,000	98	.98	5,700	55	237	0	0	6	2	.6	0	.44	.36
		7-16	11:40	99	5,130,000	99	.97	7,000	28	250	5	0	13	4	.8	0	.44	.36
		7-24	10:30	99	4,970,000	97	.97	5,400	50	232	2	1	9	6	.7	0	.44	.38
5.....	F	6-14	10:40	99	4,980,000	101	1.0	5,300	41	239	4	0	12	4	1.2	0	.42	.34
		6-21	10:15	99.2	4,830,000	99	1.0	5,600	53	226	3	0	13	5	0.6	0	.46	.34
		6-25	3:40	99	4,600,000	94	1.0	5,100	63	222	5	0	7	3	0.4	0	.44	.38
		7-1	2:15	99	4,100,000	92	1.1	5,500	49	234	3	3	8	3	0.6	0	.44	.38
		7-6	1:45	99	4,070,000	91	1.1	5,800	78	201	3	1	10	7	1.6	0	.42	.38
		7-13	12:00	98	4,020,000	85	1.0	6,000	96	187	4	0	8	5	1.4	0	.42	.38
		7-16	2:00	99.2	4,000,000	83	1.0	19,500	193	87	2	1	11	6	2.2	0	.40	.36
		7-19	2:20	96.2	3,510,000	62	.88	18,900	200	86	2	0	9	3	5.9	0.2	.40	.34
		7-21	11:30	95	2,950,000	51	.86	17,700	219	65	5	0	8	3	6.5	0.7	.38	.34
6.....	F	6-14	1:00	99.2	5,090,000	100	.98	8,500	71	180	31	2	10	6	1.7	0	.44	.36
		6-21	10:15	99.4	5,110,000	101	.98	7,300	69	188	29	0	9	5	0.7	0	.44	.36
		6-25	4:40	99.2	4,980,000	98	.99	8,100	73	183	34	0	7	3	0.8	0	.44	.36
		7-1	3:00	99.4	4,430,000	90	1.0	6,900	81	168	33	1	9	8	0.9	0	.44	.36
		7-6	2:30	99	4,530,000	91	1.0	10,500	64	194	22	0	13	7	1.2	0	.42	.36
		7-13	1:30	99	4,330,000	84	.97	6,700	92	156	38	0	10	4	2.6	0	.42	.34
		7-16	3:00	99.4	4,010,000	83	1.0	7,500	112	122	49	2	11	4	4.6	0	.42	.32
		7-19	4:00	97.4	3,720,000	66	.89	13,400	130	114	43	0	7	6	9.4	0.2	.40	.32
		7-21	12:00	97	3,050,000	51	.88	20,000	147	93	39	1	11	9	13.1	0.9	.40	.30
7.....	F	6-14	2:40	99	5,250,000	102	1.0	5,000	46	236	4	0	11	3	1.2	0	.42	.36
		6-21	1:40	98.6	5,380,000	103	.96	4,800	55	223	3	1	14	4	1.0	0	.42	.36
		6-26	9:30	99	5,370,000	103	.96	5,400	62	221	2	0	10	5	0.9	0	.42	.36
		7-2	9:00	99.2	5,270,000	102	.97	6,400	50	229	5	0	9	7	1.3	0	.42	.36
		7-6	3:35	99	4,710,000	99	1.0	6,000	73	203	3	0	18	3	1.5	0	.42	.36
		7-9*	9:00	98.6	4,230,000	88	1.0	4,200	71	197	2	1	23	6	1.7	0	.42	.34
		7-12	4:00	98	5,290,000	102	.97	4,500	112	167	4	0	13	4	1.1	0	.42	.34
		7-17	9:30	100	5,060,000	100	.99	7,200	99	174	5	0	14	8	1.6	0	.42	.34
		7-19	3:30	99.6	4,600,000	85	.92	6,100	175	98	0	3	19	5	2.3	0	.42	.34
		7-26†	8:30	95.4	3,210,000	49	.76	8,400	191	83	6	0	11	9	27.1	0.2	.38	.30
		8-9	9:00	97	4,490,000	78	.87	8,500	205	78	1	1	9	6	13.2	0	.40	.34

* Individual dose of orange juice (3 cc.) given here.

† Orange juice (2 cc.) added to the diet daily from this date.

TABLE IX—Continued
BLOOD COUNTS OF SERIES 2 GUINEA PIGS WITH SCURVY

Case	Sex	Date	Time	Temperature	Erythrocytes	Hemoglobin	Color Index	Leucocytes	Differential Count						Reticulated Erythrocytes		Nucleated Erythrocytes		Fragility		
									Polymorphonuclears	Lymphocytes	Eosinophiles	Basophiles	Mononuclears	Transitionals	%	%	Began	Complete			
8.....	F	1926																			
		6-14	3:40	99.2	5,260,000	102	1.0	4,700	49	168	56	0	20	7	%						
		6-21	1:40	99	5,190,000	101	.98	6,500	43	188	49	1	15	4	1.0	0	.42	.34			
		6-26	10:15	99.2	5,200,000	101	.97	5,300	61	167	53	0	13	6	1.3	0	.42	.34			
		7-2	10:00	99.4	5,170,000	101	.98	3,200	69	160	57	0	11	3	0.9	0	.44	.36			
		7-6	4:30	98.8	4,640,000	93	1.0	7,700	71	144	64	0	13	8	1.1	0	.42	.34			
		7-14	9:40	97.8	4,380,000	90	1.0	7,300	106	119	33	0	24	18	1.6	0	.42	.34			
7-17	10:30	96	4,950,000	92	.92	7,600	187	72	20	0	11	10	1.5	0	.42	.34					
														2.3	0	.42	.34				
9.....	F	6-15	10:45	99	5,430,000	103	.95	5,000	90	183	3	1	13	10	0.7	0	.46	.40			
		6-22	11:05	98.6	5,460,000	104	.95	4,900	93	187	2	0	11	7	0.9	0	.46	.40			
		6-23	10:10	99	5,260,000	102	.97	4,400	81	203	4	0	9	3	0.8	0	.46	.40			
		7-3	9:00	99	5,000,000	100	1.0	5,200	88	185	7	1	12	6	0.6	0	.44	.36			
		7-7	10:15	99	4,780,000	96	1.0	6,800	97	181	3	0	10	9	1.4	0	.42	.34			
		7-14	10:30	98.8	4,210,000	86	1.0	5,800	109	174	3	0	9	5	3.7	0	.42	.34			
		7-19	11:00	95.2	3,400,000	52	.86	11,200	123	144	5	3	12	8	12.00	0.2	.40	.32			
10.....	F	6-15	11:30	99.2	4,760,000	98	1.0	6,900	53	223	4	3	10	7	0.6	0	.42	.36			
		6-22	12:15	99	5,050,000	99	.98	6,500	60	223	3	0	11	3	0.5	0	.42	.36			
		6-28	11:20	99.2	5,010,000	97	.97	5,000	56	230	0	1	8	5	0.4	0	.42	.36			
		7-3	11:30	99	4,600,000	93	1.0	7,200	49	238	2	0	7	4	1.1	0	.42	.36			
		7-7	11:25	98.8	4,520,000	91	1.0	10,400	63	217	3	0	12	5	6.8	0	.42	.34			
		7-14	1:00	98.6	4,270,000	77	.90	11,400	93	189	2	2	6	3	13.6	0.1	.40	.32			
		7-19	9:00	95.8	3,800,000	57	.75	12,100	137	144	3	0	10	6	22.6	0.7	.38	.30			
11.....	F																				

‡ Removed early from group for special experiment.

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12.....	F	6-15	3:20	98.8	5,220,000	103	.99	6,000	23	258	0	0	8	7	1.2	0	.44	.40
		6-22	2:10	99	5,180,000	102	.99	5,500	57	228	6	1	5	3	0.6	0	.44	.40
		6-28	2:45	98.8	5,090,000	100	.99	9,700	46	236	3	0	7	8	0.8	0	.44	.38
		7-3	2:30	98.8	4,620,000	98	1.0	7,600	49	239	5	0	3	4	0.7	0	.44	.40
		7-7	2:45	98.8	4,450,000	97	1.0	7,100	91	193	1	0	9	6	1.1	0	.44	.38
		7-14	2:10	98.6	4,020,000	84	1.0	6,300	128	153	2	0	10	7	0.9	0	.42	.38
		7-19	1:30	96.4	3,290,000	63	.96	7,000	183	93	4	2	11	7	4.8	0.1	.40	.34
13.....	F	6-17	12:40	98.4	4,900,000	97	.97	5,400	98	169	10	2	12	9	1.7	0	.44	.36
		6-24	10:45	99.2	5,070,000	98	.97	6,200	102	179	8	0	3	8	0.9	0	.44	.36
		6-29	10:35	98.8	5,250,000	100	.95	5,000	96	174	9	1	9	11	1.6	0	.44	.36
		7-9	10:45	99	5,330,000	103	.97	5,100	99	182	5	0	7	7	1.3	0	.44	.36
		7-15	9:00	98.6	5,060,000	99	.98	5,500	106	175	6	0	8	5	1.6	0	.42	.34
		7-18	9:15	98.8	4,890,000	99	1.0	6,200	96	178	9	1	10	6	1.2	0	.44	.36
		7-20	8:45	99	5,120,000	100	.98	5,800	99	175	8	1	11	6	0.9	0	.44	.36
		7-22	8:45	99.2	5,250,000	100	.95	6,100	110	165	7	2	13	3	1.8	0	.44	.36
14.....	M	6-17	2:00	99.4	4,240,000	93	1.1	5,200	121	146	10	3	13	7	4.0	0	.44	.36
		6-24	11:40	99	4,460,000	96	1.0	5,300	98	180	8	0	9	5	2.2	0	.44	.36
		6-29	11:20	98.8	4,430,000	98	1.1	7,200	102	176	11	0	8	3	3.0	0	.44	.36
		7-9	11:35	99	5,170,000	100	.97	6,400	99	172	9	1	11	8	2.5	0	.44	.36
		7-15	9:45	98.6	4,900,000	99	1.0	6,100	111	157	8	3	14	7	2.7	0	.42	.36
		7-18	10:00	99	5,090,000	100	.99	5,900	108	173	7	2	6	4	3.1	0	.44	.34
		7-20	9:30	98.8	4,890,000	99	1.0	6,500	118	160	10	0	9	3	2.6	0	.44	.36
		7-22	9:30	99	5,200,000	101	.98	6,800	113	163	9	0	9	6	2.8	0	.44	.36
15.....	F	6-17	2:50	98.8	4,680,000	97	1.0	3,700	49	237	2	0	8	4	3.5	0	.42	.36
		6-24	1:20	99.2	4,690,000	97	1.0	3,400	61	215	5	1	10	8	3.6	0	.42	.36
		6-29	1:20	99	5,150,000	98	.95	5,500	57	218	6	0	14	6	2.7	0	.42	.36
		7-9	1:40	98.8	4,800,000	94	.98	4,700	55	225	4	0	9	7	3.1	0	.42	.36
		7-15	10:00	99	4,770,000	98	.97	5,200	49	225	5	1	13	7	2.3	0	.42	.36
		7-18	10:30	99.2	4,500,000	96	1.0	4,900	51	230	3	2	11	3	1.9	0	.40	.34
		7-20	11:00	98.6	5,310,000	100	.94	5,000	63	213	0	0	12	7	2.1	0	.42	.34
		7-22	10:50	99	4,890,000	94	.96	5,400	48	219	7	2	19	5	1.4	0	.44	.36
16.....	F	6-17	3:30	99.2	4,310,000	95	1.1	2,900	60	231	2	1	5	1	1.1	0	.42	.36
		6-24	2:25	99	5,270,000	102	.97	2,700	53	234	0	0	9	4	1.9	0	.42	.36
		6-29	2:40	98.8	4,700,000	99	1.0	3,300	48	240	1	0	8	3	1.3	0	.42	.34
		7-9	2:45	99.2	5,000,000	97	.97	3,600	61	226	1	0	6	6	1.4	0	.42	.36
		7-15	11:00	98.6	5,260,000	100	.95	3,500	65	221	0	2	5	7	1.1	0	.42	.36
		7-18	11:15	98.8	4,620,000	97	1.0	4,200	45	234	10	1	5	5	0.9	0	.42	.36
		7-20	11:50	99	5,170,000	102	.99	3,900	63	220	3	1	7	6	1.2	0	.42	.36
		7-22	11:30	98.8	4,870,000	99	1.0	3,700	72	220	1	0	3	4	0.8	0	.42	.36

The "graphs" are self-explanatory and give composite curves of all scorbutic animals in this experiment and show the relation of the time factor to the signs described above. The values plotted are taken from Tables VIII, IX, X, and XI, and are averages for all scorbutic animals (Series 1, Groups II and III of Series 2).

TABLE X
DAILY WEIGHTS OF SERIES 1*

Date	Case Number																			
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
1926																				
4-10...	645	900	860	790	860	780	865	875	705	920	730	620	760	525	650	665	695	710	185	215
4-13...	645	885	860	805	875	765	810	860	685	885	745	620	760	525	650	675	695	700	175	215
4-14...	650	885	860	810	860	765	805	860	675	885	760	630	755	510	660	680	690	700	180	220
4-15...	650	895	860	815	880	780	790	865	690	885	755	630	730	505	670	675	710	710	195	235
4-16...	635	895	860	830	890	790	785	860	690	890	765	635	725	505	660	685	695	720	195	235
4-17...	625	900	865	825	900	800	780	850	685	895	770	645	740	515	670	690	710	715	200	240
4-19...	630	895	845	770	880	800	805	840	675	885	780	635	750	520	675	700	685	715	205	235
4-20...	635	880	830	765	860	775	800	830	675	875	785	645	740	520	685	695	690	710	205	240
4-21...	645	895	815	790	890	790	815	850	675	845	800	640	740	520	675	695	695	720	210	245
4-22...	645	900	860	805	895	790	815	845	675	870	780	640	740	515	685	700	690	720	210	250
4-23...	650	910	880	815	905	785	825	855	665	875	795	655	735	520	680	705	685	725	210	240
4-24...	645	920	870	775	920	760	835	850	665	875	810	665	745	530	690	710	685	720	210	245
4-26...	655	925	870	820	910	790	830	860	660	890	810	655	750	540	695	720	695	715	215	240
4-27...	640	910	865	820	910	785	825	830	640	880	800	640	745	545	705	710	690	700	210	240
4-28...	650	930	875	815	920	790	825	810	640	875	800	660	735	530	700	700	720	715	200	215
4-29...	650	930	870	810	935	785	830	785	625	875	790	660	730	525	645	695	695	715	195	205
4-30...	640	910	855	790	915	775	820	775	610	870	800	650	725	530	645	680	690	725	195	205
5-3...	580	910	810	740	905	740	795	765	515	845	795	620	645	495	620	650	700	655	180	185
5-4...	660	880	775	765	885	760	720	750	500	845	740	590	615	475	590	645	695	625	170†	185†
5-5...	545	840	750	735	850	735	755	730	485	830	710	570	595	435	550	610	680	600	175	175
5-6...	520	800	725	705	815	700	730	705	†	815	680	545	580	410	520	590	660	585	170	185
5-7...	500	780	705	650	730	670	705	680	†	790	645	520	565	390	495	565	620	555	170	200
5-8...	490	770	695	650	755	655	685	665	†	765	640	500	550	375	480	550	595	540	165	200
5-9...								645					545							
5-10...	†	715	655	615	710	625	655	†		715	575	500	†	345	445	525	565	505	160	210
5-11...		705	635	600	690	615	635			705	555	†		325	430	520	550	500	160	205
5-12...		†	615	580	675	595	620			680	515	†		310	415	†	515	485	160	200
5-13...			600	†	660	585	610			665	†			295	400	†	490	†	140	225
5-14...			590		†	†	†			†				285	†		485	†	140	215
5-24...			†											†			†		135	270

* Weights in grams. Weighing was done as nearly as possible at the same time of day.

† Lettuce was added to the diet here. Weights considered with Nos. 19 and 20 to May 4, 1926.

‡ Column ends with death of animal.

It will be noted that Series 1 and Groups II and III of Series 2 developed scurvy while Groups I and IV, Series 2, remained normal in every respect. It is believed that these results show clearly that vitamin B as found in wheat germ, as fed, cannot in itself prevent the "apparent" paralysis or other signs of scurvy. The blood picture as well as anatomical and other findings of the affected animals in Group II, Series 2, agreed in all respects with those of Group III, Series 2, and with Series 1. In addition to the typical signs of scurvy noted in the living animal, the autopsy findings also confirmed the presence of this disease. Gross signs of infec-

TABLE XI
DAILY WEIGHTS OF SERIES 2*

Date	Case Number															
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
1926																
6-10.....	615	660														
6-11.....	605	655	305													
6-12.....	605	670	315	665												
6-14.....	595	655	320	630	870	730	495	730								
6-15.....	605	670	325	665	840	780	505	740	850	680		805				
6-16.....	600	650	340	660	800	760	500	725	840	660		800				
6-17.....	610	645	345	640	810	780	500	710	830	660		795	430	230	325	240
6-18.....	610	640	340	660	825	790	525	710	830	660		790	440	250	315	250
6-19.....	600	630	350	660	840	800	530	680	835	680		800	430	240	320	250
6-21.....	620	660	350	655	830	800	530	700	820	680		810	450	265	320	270
6-22.....	610	660	370	660	820	780	520	700	780	680		800	460	285	330	270
6-23.....	610	650	355	670	830	785	520	690	790	670		790	460	290	340	280
6-24.....	615	650	370	680	835	790	520	700	710	680		785	490	305	370	280
6-25.....	620	660	370	680	840	790	530	690	825	690		770	470	305	360	290
6-26.....	615	660	375	670	840	790	540	700	825	685		795	490	320	360	290
6-28.....	615	660	390	650	850	770	560	690	830	680		800	480	335	375	310
6-29.....	610	660	390	640	850	795	550	700	830	700		810	510	340	390	335
6-30.....	580	660	395	650	830	800	550	710	820	685		800	510	360	410	340
7-1.....	610	660	410	680	830	800	560	715	825	670		810	505	365	405	325
7-2.....	620	660	400	680	830	810	565	715	820	660		810	510	365	420	340
7-3.....	630	670	405	680	820	820	580	725	825	685		820	510	380	420	340
7-5.....	630	690	445	700	860	810	555	700	825	700		820	530	400	440	340
7-6.....	640	690	440	700	870	820	550	720	820	695		820	520	410	430	360
7-7.....	630	690	460	710	865	815	550	725	780	690		810	540	430	445	365
7-8.....	630	680	465	690	860	810	630	705	770	650		790	530	450	420	360
7-9.....	645	685	470	725	860	795	510†	690	790	640		780	545	445	460	380
7-10.....	640	690	470	725	850	790	490	680	785	620		785	540	470	465	390
7-12.....	660	695	500	720	730	745	455	635	770	590		750	550	460	470	400
7-13.....	630	700	490	710	750	740	440	660	740	565		730	550	475	475	400
7-14.....	640	695	500	705	725	720	420	570	715	555		710	570	490	480	410
7-15.....	645	715	490	695	725	710	455	555	695	530		690	570	515	490	425
7-16.....	640	725	500	725	700	690	455	550	690	520		665	580	510	490	425
7-17.....	630	705	490	730	685	675	435	540	665	510		640	580	530	500	450
7-18.....	630	690	520	740	670	640	410	520	640	490		630	580	515	515	440
7-19.....	650	675	530	750	650	620	425	500	615	465		605	575	530	505	460
7-20.....	665	695	555	750	640	600	430	†	595	†		580	580	540	500	455
7-21.....	675	720	570	760	620	590	420	†	†	†		†	575	550	510	425
7-22.....	690	725	605	770	600	†	410	†	†	†		†	585	560	510	460
7-23.....	†	†	†	†	†	†	400	†	†	†		†	†	†	†	†
7-24.....							380									
7-25.....							380									
7-26.....							365§									
7-27.....							365									
7-28.....							340									
7-29.....							340									
7-30.....							355									
7-31.....							360									
8-1.....							375									
8-2.....							385									
8-3.....							390									
8-6.....							405									
8-9.....							395									

Removed early for special experiment

* Weights in grams. Weighing was done as nearly as possible at the same time of day.

† Individual dose of orange juice (3 cc.) given here.

‡ Column ends with death of animal.

§ Orange juice (2 cc.) given by pipette daily from this date. Weights considered to July

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tion were absent in all scorbutic guinea pigs, although the possibility was borne in mind.

TABLE XII
SUMMARY OF INITIAL AND FINAL WEIGHTS AND SURVIVAL OF SERIES 1

Case No.	Sex	Weight at Beginning of Experiment in Grams	Weight at End of Experiment in Grams	Weight Lost in Grams	Percentage Weight Lost	Survival in Days
1.....	F	645	490	155	24.0	29
2.....	F	900	705	195	21.6	34
3.....	F	860	590	270	31.3	34
4.....	F	790	580	210	26.5	32
5.....	F	860	660	200	23.2	33
6.....	M	780	585	195	25.0	33
7.....	F	865	610	255	29.4	33
8.....	F	875	645	230	26.2	29
9.....	F	705	485	220	31.2	25
10.....	F	920	665	255	27.7	33
11.....	M	730	515	215	29.4	32
12.....	F	620	500	120	19.3	30
13.....	F	760	545	215	28.2	29
14.....	M	225	285	240	45.7	34
15.....	M	650	400	250	38.4	33
16.....	F	665	520	145	21.8	31
17.....	F	695	485	210	30.2	34
18.....	F	710	485	225	31.6	31
19*	F	185	170	15	8.1	28
20*	F	215	175	39	18.1	28

* Time and weight factors considered to date of addition of lettuce. (See routine weight chart—Series 1.)

CONCLUSIONS

1. Definite cytological changes occurred in the blood of guinea pigs in experimental scurvy. These changes became evident after ten days in our scorbutic diet.

2. They consist of a decrease in red blood cells, hemoglobin, and color index, an "apparent" decrease in fragility, a relative decrease in the number of lymphocytes, an absolute increase in polymorphonuclears, and an increase in reticulated and nucleated red blood cells and leucocytes.

3. The eosinophile, basophile, monocyte, and transitional cell counts were not considered characteristic of scurvy.

TABLE XIII

SUMMARY OF INITIAL AND FINAL WEIGHTS AND SURVIVAL OF SERIES 2

Case Number	Sex	Weight at Beginning of Experiment in Grams	Weight at End of Experiment in Grams	Weight Gain in Grams	Percentage Gain	Weight Lost in Grams	Percentage Lost	Duration in Days
GROUP I								
1.....	F	615	690	75	12.2	...		43
2.....	F	660	725	65	9.8	...		43
3.....	F	305	605	200	65.5	...		42
4.....	F	665	770	105	15.8	...		41
GROUP II								
5.....	F	870	600	...		270	31.0	40
6.....	F	730	590	...		140	19.1	39
7.....	F	495	365*	...		130	26.2	44
8.....	F	730	500	...		230	31.5	37
GROUP III								
9.....	F	850	595	...		255	30.0	37
10.....	F	680	465	...		215	31.6	36
11.....								
12.....	F	805	580	...		225	27.9	37
GROUP IV								
13.....	F	430	585	155	36.0	...		37
14.....	M	240	560	320	133.3	...		37
15.....	F	325	510	190	58.4	...		37
16.....	F	240	460	220	91.7	...		37

* Time and weight factors considered to date of addition of orange juice to daily rations. (See routine weight chart—Series 2.)

TABLE XIV

SUMMARY OF WEIGHTS AND SURVIVAL OF SERIES 1 AND SERIES 2 PIGS

Series	Group	Average Weight Lost in Grams	Average Loss %	Average Weight Gain in Grams	Average Gain %	Average Duration in Days
1.....	..	193.9	26.8			31.2
2.....	II	192.5	26.9			40.0
2.....	III	231.0	29.8			36.6
2.....	I			111.2	25.8	42.2
2.....	IV			221.2	79.8	37.0

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